

Investigating the Impact of Facial Expression Recognition in Healthcare

Benedetta Catanzariti, University of Edinburgh
benedetta.catanzariti@ed.ac.uk

This fellowship ran from January-May 2023 as part of BRAID.

BRAID is a UK-wide programme dedicated to integrating Arts and Humanities research more fully into the Responsible AI ecosystem, as well as bridging the divides between academic, industry, policy and regulatory work on responsible AI. Funded by the Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC), BRAID represents AHRC's major investment in enabling responsible AI in the UK. The Programme runs from 2022 to 2028. Working in partnership with the Ada Lovelace Institute and BBC, BRAID supports a network of interdisciplinary researchers and partnering organisations through the delivery of funding calls, community building events, and a series of programmed activities. Funding reference: Arts and Humanities Research Council grant number AH/X007146/1.

Learn more at www.braiduk.org

This research was supported via UK Research and Innovation by the R&D Science and Analysis Programme at the Department for Culture, Media & Sport. Any primary research, subsequent findings or recommendations do not represent Government views or policy and are produced according to research ethics, quality assurance, and academic independence.

To request an alternative format of this report please email braid@ed.ac.uk.

Table of Contents

Abstract	3
Introduction	4
Executive Summary	4
Background.....	7
Social and Ethical Impact	11
Recommendations.....	18
Further Questions	21
References	23

● ● ● Abstract

Over the past few years, we have witnessed a rise in the development of machine learning-based tools providing various forms of personalised healthcare. This trend has been accelerated by the Covid-19 pandemic. Among these tools are facial expression recognition (FER) applications that make use of machine learning techniques to track and predict mental health and neurodevelopmental disorders and assess pain levels based on changes in facial affective behaviours. Scholars and advocacy groups have, however, pointed to the potential of these tools to propagate pseudoscientific and harmful assumptions about people's identity based on outer appearances. This report asks: 1. What assumptions shape the development of this technology and how can we make these more transparent? 2. What are the risks of embedding this technology within healthcare infrastructures? 3. How can policy address these risks? There is a growing consensus that regulators and practitioners should strive to anticipate potential harm; however, clear guidance for the governance of these tools is at an early stage or hard to operationalise. This report offers a discussion of the key social and ethical challenges of FER technology and argues for a nuanced understanding of the harms deriving from these systems beyond data protection concerns. Finally, it offers a series of recommendations for regulators to identify and address harm.

● ● ● Introduction

The public sector increasingly relies on artificial intelligence (AI) driven systems to cope with vast amounts of available data and improve decision-making in various contexts, such as healthcare and social work. However, experts often need help to make informed judgements based on AI-generated outputs and lose their agency and ability to apply their expertise. Explainable AI techniques could provide a solution, but they are often ineffective, and even misleading, when used in expert contexts.

Based on the literature review and a preliminary contextual enquiry study with science experts and AI developers, this report provides an overview of challenges faced when introducing AI-driven decision support systems (DSSs) in practice. It discusses the role of explainability in supporting experts and outlines recommendations for how explanations could enable effective human–AI collaboration.

● ● ● Executive Summary

Facial expression recognition (FER) is a technology designed to track and classify facial expressive behaviours and produce some form of meaningful knowledge about people based on those behaviours. This report investigates the **impact of FER systems in healthcare contexts**. Here, these tools are designed to detect and assess mental health conditions (depression and anxiety), neurodevelopmental disorders (autism, bipolar disorders, and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder or ADHD), and assess pain levels on the basis of facial expressions. Many have pointed to the **limitations of these systems**, as well as the **privacy risks** associated with their use in high-stakes contexts. This report highlights the **broader societal impact** of these technologies and offers recommendations to identify and address harm.

In particular, this report asks:

1. **What assumptions shape the development of this technology and how can we make these more transparent?**
2. **What are the risks of embedding this technology within healthcare infrastructures?**
3. **How can policy address these risks?**

This research is based on a four-year **doctoral project** in science and technology studies, which combined document analysis with qualitative interviews of academic and industry machine-learning practitioners developing FER models¹. Drawing from science and technology studies, critical studies of AI and machine learning, and scholarship on disability and technology, this document aims to support policy-makers and policy analysts in governing FER systems.

The report identifies three **key challenges** of FER systems in healthcare:

Data Protection Challenges

Privacy scholars and advocates have pointed to the many issues arising from the deployment of FER systems and the lack of adequate legal safeguards. This report outlines three main challenges: control over data, processing of special category data, and bias and discrimination.

Discursive Harms

AI systems can reinforce and reproduce normative models of disability and mental health which can prove harmful to vulnerable and marginalised users. Care should be taken to avoid harmful assumptions being encoded in automated forms of mental health detection and assessment.

¹ Catanzariti, B. (2023). *Seeing Affect. Knowledge Infrastructures in Facial Expression Recognition*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation. Science, Technology and Innovation Studies. School of Social and Political Science. University of Edinburgh.

Entrenched Harms

AI-enabled medical errors and biases can have a disparate impact on vulnerable patients and their ability to self-advocate. It is important that regulators and practitioners consider the risks deriving from automation bias and black-box decision-making.

Following from these considerations, the report offers **three main recommendations:**

Extend Regulatory Frameworks to Address Specific Uses of FER in Healthcare

Current regulatory tools and proposals focus on the risks deriving from emotion recognition and are therefore inadequate to address the specific harms of FER systems in healthcare contexts. The report argues for the need to extend the remit of investigation of FER systems to include uses outside those explicitly centred around emotional inference.

Promote Multi-Stakeholders Engagement

Collaboration with other forms of knowledge and expertise, such as disability scholarship and advocacy, can help regulators and practitioners critically engage with and anticipate the societal and ethical implications of FER applications in high-stakes contexts.

Develop Strategies to Define Responsibility Beyond Data Protection and Technical Fairness

It is important that meaningful information about underlying assumptions, methods used, and explanations of system aims and outputs are available to patients and clinicians. When using FER systems in healthcare, it is essential that meaningful information about the decision-making process be available for both clinician and patient scrutiny, irrespective of data literacy levels and technical skills.

Given the growing popularity of automated behaviour analysis tools, regulators have an important role to play in ensuring that these systems avoid causing or reinforcing

social harm. It is especially important that regulators and developers collaborate with diverse groups working on the societal and ethical implications of machine learning. At the same time, regulators should ensure that relevant stakeholders can understand and meaningfully contest automated decision-making resulting from these systems.

● ● ● Background

1.1 What is Facial Expression Recognition?

Machine learning systems are becoming increasingly common in modern healthcare provision, often claimed to support clinicians' objective decision-making and improve patient diagnoses and treatments. Among these are facial expression recognition (FER) systems, that is, supervised or semi-supervised machine learning tools designed to predict, diagnose, and manage a range of mental health and neurodevelopmental conditions (including depression, anxiety, ADHD, autism, and bipolar disorder), prevent suicide, as well as assess pain levels, based on changes in facial expressions. These tools can be seen as part of a larger project of digitisation of healthcare called digital phenotyping, the analysis of people's interactions with technology to infer markers of health (Jain et al, 2015). In recent years, these digitalisation efforts have been extended beyond physical health and applied to mental health as well, a process accelerated by the Covid-19 pandemic (Birk et al, 2021; Baumeister & Montag, 2023). It is important to note the commercial incentives behind these projects, the digitalisation of mental healthcare and, particularly, the role played by big tech corporations in promoting these methods. In 2017, the former director of the National Institute of Mental Health (NIMH), Thomas Insel, became a vocal advocate for the application of data-driven technology to mental health (Insel, 2017). At the time, Insel had left his role as director of the institute to take on a leading role at Google's parent company Alphabet (Stark, 2020). These digitalisation efforts have given rise to the proliferation of commercial and (although mostly at a research stage) clinical tools designed to provide forms of personalised and accessible mental healthcare (Birk et al, 2021).

FER systems belong to a family of technologies termed “affective computing”, an interdisciplinary research area bridging computer science, engineering, and psychology, dedicated to the development of computer systems trained to recognise and simulate human affective behaviours (Picard, 2000). To recognise expressive behaviours, a machine learning algorithm identifies “key landmarks” on the face – such as the tip of the nose, the corners of the lips, or the arches of the eyebrows – and uses these coordinates to classify facial expressions according to a narrow taxonomy of affective behaviours (Figure 1). The most popular approach to affective behaviours is grounded on the “classical view of emotions” (Barrett, 2017) which posits the existence of discrete or “basic”, biologically determined expressions of emotions (e.g. anger, joy, sadness, disgust, fear, and surprise) that can be measured objectively and classified through computational techniques (Ekman, 1970; Ekman & Friesen, 1971).

Figure 1. Noldus Facial Expression Recognition Software, <https://www.noldus.com>

However, **these methods have been widely contested** as they are premised on the assumption that outer appearances can provide accurate and objective indications of mental and emotional states across individuals and cultures. In a comprehensive meta-review of the literature on emotional inference and facial expressions, psychologist Lisa Feldman Barrett and colleagues have argued that the **available evidence fails to support a cross-cultural view of basic emotional expressions**, and that the ways in which people communicate emotions vary significantly across cultures, and even in considering the same individual (Barrett et al, 2019). Further, as many have noted, AI systems claiming to produce meaningful knowledge about individuals based on their physical appearance can propagate **harmful assumptions** grounded in **“scientifically baseless, racist, and discredited pseudoscientific fields”** (Stark & Hutson, 2021: 4–5). Critics refer here to the 19th century practice of **physiognomy**, the widespread belief that a person’s facial appearance could reveal something about their moral character. As many have argued, the **resurgence of physiognomic claims in computer science practice requires urgent attention** as it poses a threat to human and civil rights (Arcas, 2017; Birhane, 2021; Sloane et al, 2022).

1.2 Affective Computing in Healthcare

Healthcare applications of FER systems use emotional expressions as an indication of the likelihood of a particular psychological or clinical state (e.g. the facial expressions associated with the emotion “sadness” are considered indicative of particular degrees of depression) (He et al, 2022). Currently, developments are focused on the following areas:

Mobile Health (mHealth):

Commercial applications in this area include self-management of mental health and symptom tracking (e.g. mood tracking) that may combine facial expression data with other behaviour data sources (e.g. other physiological data or self-reported mood

data). These applications are designed to provide personalised insights and recommendations and improve user wellbeing.

Human Research Behaviour:

Applications in this space are designed and developed to support a wide range of research areas including developmental research, research on mental health, research on autism, bipolar disorders, and ADHD, and neuroscience research. Researchers use FER systems in combination with other physiological sensors (e.g. eye tracking, heart rate sensors, etc.) to obtain insights on human behaviour.

Clinical Research and Development (R&D):

Applications in this area are envisaged to support clinical R&D processes. These include the use of FER systems to assess the efficacy of medication by, for instance, monitoring pain levels or the progress of depressive states based on facial expressions.

Clinical Diagnosis and Treatment:

FER systems in this domain are designed to support professional decision-making in clinical settings (e.g. diagnostic aids for the automatic detection of clinical states and neurodevelopmental disorders).

At this stage, most efforts are focused on **mobile health** and **human research behaviour**. However, many (UK and EU) FER companies have started to include **clinical research and development** and **clinical diagnosis and treatment** applications in their R&D departments. These tools are often envisioned and marketised as diagnostic aids that could support healthcare providers in making “more accurate” and “more objective” health diagnoses. However, it is important to be aware of the limitations, as well as the socio-ethical challenges posed by these systems.

● ● ● Social and Ethical Impact

Scholars, civil society, and regulators have pointed to the risks associated with the use of affective technologies, particularly with regards to data protection and data accuracy. These are summarised below in section 2.1. However, this report argues that the use of FER systems in healthcare contexts carries specific and additional risks, outlined in section 2.2 and section 2.3. In particular, these sections shed light on the power of FER systems to **normalise stereotypical and harmful assumptions around health and disability**, as well as the **risks of embedding these assumptions within wider healthcare infrastructures and practices**.

2.1 Data Protection Challenges

FER systems are considered “**soft biometrics**” or “generation 3 technologies”, that is to say, biometric technologies used to track and classify those “physiological and psychological aspects of a person that can shift depending on time or circumstance, or both. This includes behaviours and emotions, as well as modalities such as gait and facial analysis, where age, injury or illness may alter the data provided” (ICO, 2022b). Privacy scholars and advocates have pointed to the many issues arising from the deployment of these tools and the lack of adequate legal safeguards. This section outlines three main challenges: control over data, processing of special category data, and bias and discrimination.

Control Over Data:

FER systems are claimed to be able to infer psychological and mental states that the user is not aware of, or is not “trusted” to relay accurately (McStay, 2018). As highlighted by the Information Commissioner’s Office (ICO), this constitutes a novel and challenging form of data processing, in that, while users are typically conscious of the modalities in which personal data is provided, **FER systems rely on subconscious behaviours, further obscuring practices of data processing** (ICO, 2022a).

Processing of Special Category Data:

Image data acquired and processed through FER systems is not used to directly identify a natural person and, therefore, **does not fall under Article 6** of the **UK GDPR definition of special category data (GDPR 2016)**. However, **this data constitutes biometric data** and it might be used by third parties to identify individuals or infer health information. This is especially relevant in the context of FER systems used in the **mobile health industry**, where the data collected through mood tracking practices is not used for diagnostic purposes but could, in the event of **data breach** or **function creep** (the repurposing of data beyond the originally intended uses), be **used to infer personal or health information about users**.

Bias and Discrimination:

Following a mounting body of work presenting evidence of the societal harms, and particularly racial discrimination, propagated by AI systems, scholars have pointed to the disparate impact that FER systems can have on marginalised groups. In a comparative analysis of commercial FER systems Microsoft AI and Face++, researcher Lauren Rhue showed that both **systems attributed more negative emotions to black men** than their white counterparts (Rhue 2018). Similarly, research has shown that **FER algorithms can misinterpret physical impairments and medical conditions**, resulting in misclassification. This type of analysis is part of a broader scholarship on bias and fairness in automated systems that, by auditing different commercial software, has, in recent years, brought to the fore the **disparate impact that computer vision systems have on black and indigenous people, people of colour, gender nonconforming individuals, and disabled people** (Buolamwini & Gebru, 2018; Raji & Fried, 2021; Scheuerman et al., 2020; O. Keyes, 2018; Os Keyes, 2020).

2.2 Beyond Data Protection: Discursive Harms

Governance interventions that focus solely on data protection risk overlooking what scholars have called **“discursive”** or **“epistemic” harms** (Hoffmann, 2019), that is, harms occurring “when and how data-driven decision making (in theory or in practice)

affects how we come to know things, reduces who has the ability to ‘know’ in a meaningful way, and narrows what can be known at all [emphasis added]” (Os Keyes, 2019). Discursive harm takes place when algorithmic decision-making produces or consolidates harmful assumptions about, for instance, health and disability. In this sense, scholars have argued that technical and legal analyses of harm and discrimination would benefit from a **deeper and broader investigation of the “potential negative externalities” of algorithmic technologies** (Peña Gangadharan & Niklas, 2019: 896). This can be done by parsing the historical and cultural assumptions that inform the development of automated systems. To this end, **Box 1** provides a brief historical perspective on the use of affective data and its potential harms. The remainder of this section discusses the normalising power of facial expression classification on vulnerable users in healthcare contexts.

Box 1. Perspective: Historical Context of Affective Data

The scientific measurement of affective behaviour is not new. Historians of science have identified its origin in late-nineteenth and early-twentieth laboratory sciences (Dror, 1999b; 1999a; Martin Moruno, 2016). Enabled by new technologies and recording procedures, physiologists and clinicians elevated affective behaviour to an object of scientific inquiry. These classification efforts led to catalogues of emotional types, often reflecting social hierarchies that opposed the composed and sophisticated affective expressions of European men to those of women, people of colour, criminals, and “the insane” (Dror, 2001). This scientific effort to measure, quantify, and display emotions served as a way to corroborate and normalise implicit or explicit assumptions or expectations towards affective behaviour. This transformation of emotions into an object of scientific knowledge, along with the rise of mechanical forms of affective measurements, resonates with the broader cultural transformation of Western sciences in the late 19th century, seeking to anchor human experience into biological and quantifiable truths. According to its proponents, this new physiology of emotions would shed light on the underlying causes of social ills – fatigue, insanity, or criminality – and encourage the reproduction of productive,

sane, and “fit” individuals, facilitating the discrimination of already marginalised groups.

This brief historical perspective is useful in that it points to the normative power of affect classification (the power of shaping how others express and perceive emotions), and it places automated forms of affective behaviour analysis into a larger historical trend that, shaped by social and cultural factors, seeks to measure and quantify human affective experience to promote certain affective expressions over others.

Media scholars have noted how current techniques of affect classification and representation echoes these older ways of using affective data and, in particular, that mood and emotion tracking technologies can reinforce the expression of a hierarchy of feelings aligned with dominant socio-cultural norms (Stark, 2020). As explored in the next sections, one major challenge in this regard is the potential impact that these systems can have on neurodiverse or disabled users. AI systems that target autistic people, for example, can “embody normative expectations of a neurotypical society, which predominantly views autism as a medical deficit in need of ‘correction’” (Spiel et al., 2019: 1). This is of particular importance when considering the use of affective technologies used to detect and treat mental health and neurodevelopmental disorders based on outer appearances.

Scholars and advocacy groups have pointed to the potential of machine learning systems to propagate harmful assumptions about users’ identity and social outcome based on facial and bodily appearances as well as reinforce normative ideas about expressive behaviours. In particular, work in this area has noted how **AI systems can produce and reinforce a normative model of illness and disability**. In this sense, AI systems that aim to detect disability or mental health issues often “construct categories of ‘disabled’ and ‘non-disabled’ based not on people’s lived experience or identity preference, but on **assumptions embedded in the data researchers and tech**

companies have access to” (Mills & Whittaker, 2019: 21). Further, disability scholars have noted that **two individuals can experience the same disability or illness in very different ways** depending on different aspects of their identity, such as gender, race, class, and age. In addition to this, it is important to note that **racial, gender, and cultural biases in mental health diagnoses** are already **well documented in non-automated diagnostic methods** (Garb, 2021) and are likely to be encoded and replicated by automated systems.

Another important point of consideration is the **binding effect** that these systems can have for disabled users. When tracking devices become an essential part of patient care plans, privacy is “something that disabled people aren’t able to choose” (Mills & Whittaker, 2019: 23). **Companies can extract value from user data that disabled and ill people cannot refuse to share.** In view of these concerns around meaningful consent and the potential for harm, practitioners and regulators are encouraged to move beyond discussions on bias, technical errors, and data protection and ask broader questions such as **what standards of “normal”, “health”, and “ability” are produced and reinforced by these systems?** How can users and patients challenge automated diagnoses and interventions? For example, FER systems that help neurodiverse users to understand and display facial expressions can encode standards and expectations of a neurotypical society (Spiel et al, 2019). Efforts to “de-bias” datasets and include more data about disabled and neurodiverse people can also be problematic, especially when the data used to train FER algorithms are curated by observer annotators who label data out of context, and based on assumptions and expectations (see **Box 2: The role of perception in FER systems**).

In the words of Meredith Whittaker and colleagues, “what kinds of design, research, and AI engineering practices could produce more desirable futures for disabled people? How can we assess the effects of these practices, and what other systemic interventions might be needed, beyond those focused on the technology itself?” (Mills & Whittaker, 2019: 3).

Box 2. The Role of Perception in FER Systems: Automated Pain Assessment

FER systems typically rely on **supervised or semi-supervised machine learning** techniques, that is, algorithms trained on labelled datasets containing images or videos of facial expressions. These images are **annotated by human observers** (data annotators) who assign numerical values to individual facial movements (e.g. the lowering of the eyebrows or the raising of the lip corners), which are then associated with particular meanings (e.g. emotional expressions or mental health conditions). In the case of automated pain detection, facial movements are associated with pain scores. These methods are claimed to provide objective assessments of pain, particularly in cases where patients are unable to self-report pain levels (Alghamdi & Alaghband, 2022). Despite these claims, it is important to note the **role of annotators' perception in automated behaviour analysis**.

For instance, regulators and practitioners should be aware of existing biases in non-automated forms of pain assessment. One important point of consideration is the **documented racial and gender bias in non-automated pain detection and assessment**. Research has indeed shown that **pain is often underestimated in women and people of colour**, as gender and race stereotypes can affect how pain is perceived in others (Zhang et al, 2021; Hoffman et al, 2016). While FER systems aim to address these issues by making pain detection more objective and reliable, it is important to ask how perceiver biases are addressed within the design and development pipeline. For example, regulators and practitioners **should consider how potential biases can be encoded within the training stage** (data collection, cleaning, and annotation) of machine learning models.

In addition, studies have shown how **socio-cultural factors can influence the expression (not just the perception) of pain**. Literature on pain distinguishes “nociception” (the neurophysiological process of encoding and transmitting stimuli to the central nervous system as a result of physical tissue damage) from pain (a more “reflective” process of receiving and processing stimuli that is shaped by biological,

psychological, and socio-cultural factors). In this regard, Gadi Gilam and colleagues argue that “pain is a contextualised, multidimensional construct resulting from interactions of peripheral and central nervous systems with potential external factors, but that in itself cannot be reduced to peripheral activity in sensory pathways” (Gilam et al, 2020: 18). This means that **people can experience pain differently depending on various factors**, including access to (or absence of) a support system, continuous exposure to discriminatory healthcare practices, as well as thoughts, beliefs, and expectations around pain and treatment (Gilam et al, 2020). It is important to be aware of these dimensions when assessing the claims of automated classification systems.

2.3 Entrenching Harm

A final form of harm relevant to these tools is the entrenchment of these normalising assumptions within larger socio-technical systems. An example of this is the incorporation of FER systems into medical research and healthcare provision. For example, the use of this technology to evaluate mental health treatments in clinical trials can further complicate the opacity of these systems. **What happens when the assumptions underlying FER models “disappear” within these larger infrastructures?**

Extensive research has documented the risks of **automation bias** or automation complacency, that is, a **tendency to over-rely on computer-generated predictions without investigating for alternative information** (Challen et al, 2019; Arnold, 2021; Alberdi et al, 2005). This can happen due to the predictions confirming the clinician’s cognitive bias or because of the system’s lack of interpretability. In response to the latter problem – the “black boxed” nature of machine learning models – the field of so-called explainable AI (XAI) has offered various technical solutions, such as risk scores and visualization methods. However, as both researchers and clinicians have pointed out, these explanations do not always translate in the context of clinical practice (Tonekaboni et al, 2019), leading to **potential misdiagnosis and mistreatment**.

In addition to **eroding clinician trust in automated systems**, AI-enabled medical errors and biases can have a **disparate impact on vulnerable patients and their ability to self-advocate**. It is important that regulators and practitioners consider the risks deriving from automation bias and black-box decision-making. Robert Challen and colleagues offer a list of useful questions to anticipate potential harm, such as: “How is the system going to be monitored and maintained over time to adjust for prediction drift? Does the system adjust its behaviour (‘err on the side of caution’) where there are high impact negative outcomes? Can the system identify ‘out of sample’ input and adjust its confidence accordingly? Are the system’s predictions interpretable? Does it produce an estimate of confidence? How is the certainty of prediction communicated to clinicians to avoid automation bias? How can it accommodate breaking changes to clinical practice? What aspects of existing clinical practice does this system reinforce?” (Challen et al, 2019: 235).

● ● ● Recommendations

In light of these social and ethical challenges, the last section of this report offers three recommendations for regulators: **Extend regulatory frameworks to address specific uses of FER in healthcare; Promote multi-stakeholder engagement; and Develop strategies to define responsibility beyond data protection and technical fairness.**

3.1 Extend Regulatory Frameworks to Address Specific Uses of FER in Healthcare

Currently, the proposed European Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act) will, once enacted, be the only regulatory tool addressing the specific risks deriving from the use of affective technologies, or “emotion recognition”. However, the AI Act classifies emotion recognition systems as “low or minimal risk”, and only requires developers to disclose the use of these tools to users. As many have noted, however, the limitations of these systems, coupled with the social and ethical challenges outlined in this report, can pose a **threat to human rights** (Article 19, 2021; Stark & Hutson, 2021). In

October 2022, the ICO issued a warning to organisations, citing the current **“immature” state of emotion recognition technology and its potential for bias and discrimination.**² In response, scholars and civil society organisations have argued for the **recategorization of emotion recognition technologies into “unacceptable risks and prohibited AI practices”** (Article 5 of the AI Act) (Ada Lovelace Institute, 2022). However, **uses of FER systems in healthcare contexts** (the assessments of mental health, pain, and neurodevelopmental conditions) **do not involve inferences about emotional states** (they do not, explicitly or implicitly, seek to infer emotions nor intentions from facial behaviours). Therefore, **extending the remit of investigation of FER systems to include uses outside of those explicitly centred around emotional inference** can contribute to UK policy interventions aiming to reduce harm and discrimination.

3.2 Promote Multi-Stakeholder Engagement

Cross-disciplinarity and stakeholder engagement remain a challenge in machine learning practice. In addition, inflated expectations around the capabilities of AI and machine learning, as well as financial and organisational constraints, can further disincentivise meaningful collaboration and participation. Nonetheless, partnering with other forms of knowledge and expertise can help practitioners and regulators critically engage with and anticipate the societal and ethical implications of machine learning applications in high-stake contexts.

When designing affective technologies for mental healthcare, **disability scholars, mental health and chronic health advocates, clinicians, and researchers and advocates in the area of algorithmic injustice can all provide significant perspective on the risks and benefits of the use of affective data.** Importantly, these disciplines have highlighted the importance of centring the experience of those who are most impacted by technology’s development and application. **Participatory approaches to**

² <https://ico.org.uk/about-the-ico/media-centre/news-and-blogs/2022/10/immature-biometric-technologies-could-be-discriminating-against-people-says-ico-in-warning-to-organisations/>, accessed 23/07/2024.

both policy and innovation that involve multiple stakeholders (such as healthcare professionals and patients) have proven to be valuable methods to overcome ethical challenges arising from the application of technology in complex settings such as healthcare.

Importantly, practitioners and regulators should be careful not to adopt participation as a mere form of “consultation” but rather as a form of justice: as a “top-down design process”, consultation can often take “the form of ‘designing for’ a particular group without an ongoing commitment to their inclusion in the process, and systemic inequalities can be hard-coded into consultation and representation protocols” (Sloane et al, 2020). **Participation as justice**, on the other hand, requires that all stakeholders create “ongoing relationships based on mutual benefit, reciprocity, equity and justice” (Sloane et al, 2020). In this sense, participation should allow stakeholders to challenge or contest not only the technology’s aims and assumptions, but also the methods and forms of participation itself (Stilgoe, Owen, & Macnaghten, 2013). While financial, organisational, and institutional constraints might make this form of participation harder to achieve, it is nonetheless important that regulators and practitioners aim to create **genuine and long-term forms of stakeholder inclusion**.

3.3 Develop Strategies to Define Responsibility Beyond Data Protection and Technical Fairness

A final recommendation for regulators is to **enable and promote auditing mechanisms to document the normative assumptions** that inform the development and use of FER systems (and machine learning systems more broadly). As some have noted, this form of “**epistemic auditing**” can help “reveal discriminatory effects that the creators of the tool would classify as ‘unintentional’ and that can point toward the construct itself as being problematic or discriminatory by design” (Sloane et al, 2022: 6). In this sense, **challenging the framings and scopes of these systems can help promote forms of accountability beyond technical fairness and legal compliance**, and better address societal harm and adverse outcome.

Research in this area has shown how **documentation of data curation practices** can improve public and organisational trust in automated systems. Margaret Mitchell and colleagues have suggested the implementation of brief documents – “model cards” – that include meaningful information about every trained model, such as “what assumptions were made during its development, what type of model behaviour different cultural, demographic, or phenotypic population groups may experience, and an evaluation of how well the model performs with respect to those groups” (Mitchell et al, 2019: 3). Model cards should also include primary intended uses and users, and out-of-scope uses and users. Similarly, Timnit Gebru and colleagues have designed a set of questions – “datasheets for datasets” – to encourage dataset creators to reflect on the overall process of data curation including collection, cleaning, labelling, uses, distribution, maintenance, and impact (Gebru et al., 2020). Other documentation efforts aim at fostering inter-organizational accountability and transparency (Miceli et al, 2021).

Some of the **broader questions** that regulators and practitioners could ask include: What are the motivations underlying these systems? Are these motivations transparent and in the public interest? What methods and forms of knowledge/expertise have shaped these aims? Which groups/communities are these systems benefitting (directly or indirectly)? Which groups/communities are they instead excluding (directly or indirectly)? What problem are these systems addressing? Who formulated the problem? How were the data and methods chosen? How will it be measured whether these meet the stakeholder needs?

● ● ● Further Questions

This report has sought to investigate FER systems analytically and offer strategies for grounding the historical, social, and cultural assumptions that inform their development. However, the recommendations discussed here can be extended to algorithmic technologies more broadly to include, for instance, machine learning systems designed to track and predict mental health based on different sources of data (e.g. text, speech, and voice data, or data collected through other physiological

or behavioural sensors). In particular, recommendations 3.2 and 3.3 would allow regulators and practitioners to challenge developers' claims and identify risks and harms in a timely manner.

Finally, this report has largely focused on harms, based on the mounting body of work pointing to the limitations and risks of FER systems. However, the report makes a case that positive uses and benefits of these tools can only be identified and co-created by including stakeholders' participation in all stages of the development lifecycle, including the initial framing of the technology's aims and scope.

● ● ● References

1. Ada Lovelace Institute. 2022. 'People, Risk and the Unique Requirements of AI. 18 Recommendations to Strengthen the EU AI Act'. <https://www.adalovelaceinstitute.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/Policy-briefing-People-risk-and-the-unique-requirements-of-AI-18-recommendations-to-strengthen-the-EU-AI-Act.pdf>, accessed 21.05.2024.
2. Alberdi, Eugenio, Peter Ayton, Andrey Povyakalo, and L. Strigini. 2005. 'Automation Bias and System Design: A Case Study in a Medical Application'. In *IEE and MOD HFI DTC Symposium on People and Systems - Who are we Designing for?*, 2005 p. 53 – 60. <https://doi.org/10.1049/ic:20050451>, accessed 21.05.2024.
3. Alghamdi, Thoria, and Gita Alaghand. 2022. 'Facial Expressions Based Automatic Pain Assessment System'. *Applied Sciences* 12 (13): 6423. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12136423>, accessed 21.05.2024.
4. Arcas, Blaise Aguera y. 2017. 'Physiognomy's New Clothes'. Medium. 20 May 2017. <https://medium.com/@blaisea/physiognomys-new-clothes-f2d4b59fdd6a>, accessed 21.05.2024.
5. Arnold, Mark Henderson. 2021. 'Teasing out Artificial Intelligence in Medicine: An Ethical Critique of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning in Medicine'. *Journal of Bioethical Inquiry*, January, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11673-020-10080-1>, accessed 21.05.2024.
6. Article 19. 2021. 'Emotional Entanglement: China's Emotion Recognition Market and Its Implications for Human Rights'. <https://www.article19.org/emotion-recognition-technology-report/>, accessed 21.05.2024.
7. Barrett, Lisa Feldman. 2017. *How Emotions Are Made: The Secret Life of the Brain*. Pan Macmillan.
8. Barrett, Lisa Feldman, Ralph Adolphs, Stacy Marsella, Aleix M. Martinez, and Seth D. Pollak. 2019. 'Emotional Expressions Reconsidered: Challenges to Inferring Emotion From Human Facial Movements': *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, July. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1529100619832930>, accessed 21.05.2024.
9. Baumeister, Harald, and Christian Montag. 2023. 'Digital Phenotyping and Mobile Sensing in Psychoinformatics—A Rapidly Evolving Interdisciplinary Research Endeavor'. In *Digital Phenotyping and Mobile Sensing: New*

- Developments in Psychoinformatics*, edited by Christian Montag and Harald Baumeister, 1–9. *Studies in Neuroscience, Psychology and Behavioral Economics*. Cham: Springer International Publishing.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-98546-2_1, accessed 21.05.2024.
10. Birhane, Abeba. 2021. 'Cheap AI'. In *Fake AI*, edited by Frederike Kaltheuner. Meatspace Press.
 11. Birk, Rasmus, Anna Lavis, Federica Lucivero, and Gabrielle Samuel. 2021. 'For What It's Worth. Unearthing the Values Embedded in Digital Phenotyping for Mental Health'. *Big Data & Society* 8 (2): 20539517211047320.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/20539517211047319>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 12. Buolamwini, Joy, and Timnit Gebru. 2018. 'Gender Shades: Intersectional Accuracy Disparities in Commercial Gender Classification'. In *Proceedings of the 1st Conference on Fairness, Accountability and Transparency*, 77–91. PMLR. <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v81/buolamwini18a.html>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 13. Challen, Robert, Joshua Denny, Martin Pitt, Luke Gompels, Tom Edwards, and Krasimira Tsaneva-Atanasova. 2019. 'Artificial Intelligence, Bias and Clinical Safety'. *BMJ Quality & Safety* 28 (3): 231–37.
<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjqs-2018-008370>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 14. Dror, Otniel E. 1999a. 'The Affect of Experiment: The Turn to Emotions in Anglo-American Physiology, 1900-1940'. *Isis* 90 (2): 205–37.
 15. ———. 1999b. 'The Scientific Image of Emotion: Experience and Technologies of Inscription'. *Configurations* 7 (3): 355–401.
 16. ———. 2001. 'Counting the Affects: Discoursing in Numbers'. *Social Research* 68 (2): 357–78.
 17. Ekman, Paul. 1970. 'Universal Facial Expressions of Emotion'. *California Mental Health Research Digest* 8: 151–58.
 18. Ekman, Paul, and Wallace V. Friesen. 1971. 'Constants across Cultures in the Face and Emotion'. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 17 (2): 124–29. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0030377>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 19. Garb, Howard N. 2021. 'Race Bias and Gender Bias in the Diagnosis of Psychological Disorders'. *Clinical Psychology Review* 90 (December): 102087.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2021.102087>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 20. Gebru, Timnit, Jamie Morgenstern, Briana Vecchione, Jennifer Wortman Vaughan, Hanna Wallach, Hal Daumé III, and Kate Crawford. 2020. 'Datasheets for Datasets'. ArXiv:1803.09010 [Cs], March.

- <http://arxiv.org/abs/1803.09010>, accessed 21.05.2024.
21. Gilam, Gadi, James J. Gross, Tor D. Wager, Francis J. Keefe, and Sean C. Mackey. 2020. 'What Is the Relationship between Pain and Emotion? Bridging Constructs and Communities'. *Neuron* 107 (1): 17–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2020.05.024>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 22. He, Lang, Mingyue Niu, Prayag Tiwari, Pekka Marttinen, Rui Su, Jiewei Jiang, Chenguang Guo, Hongyu Wang, Songtao Ding, Zhongmin Wang, Wei Dang, Xiaoying Pan. 2022. 'Deep Learning for Depression Recognition with Audiovisual Cues: A Review'. *Information Fusion* 80 (April): 56–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inffus.2021.10.012>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 23. Hoffman, Kelly M., Sophie Trawalter, Jordan R. Axt, and M. Norman Oliver. 2016. 'Racial Bias in Pain Assessment and Treatment Recommendations, and False Beliefs about Biological Differences between Blacks and Whites'. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 113 (16): 4296–4301. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1516047113>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 24. Hoffmann, Anna Lauren. 2019. 'Where Fairness Fails: Data, Algorithms, and the Limits of Antidiscrimination Discourse'. *Information, Communication & Society* 22 (7): 900–915. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2019.1573912>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 25. ICO. 2022a. 'Biometrics: Foresight'. Information Commissioner's Office.
 26. ———. 2022b. 'Biometrics: Insight'. Information Commissioner's Office.
 27. Insel, Thomas R. 2017. 'Digital Phenotyping: Technology for a New Science of Behavior'. *JAMA* 318 (13): 1215–16. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2017.11295>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 28. Jain, Sachin H., Brian W. Powers, Jared B. Hawkins, and John S. Brownstein. 2015. 'The Digital Phenotype'. *Nature Biotechnology* 33 (5): 462–63. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt.3223>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 29. Keyes, O. 2018. 'The Misgendering Machines'. *Trans/HCI implications of automatic gender recognition. Proceedings of the ACM on human-computer interaction*, 2(CSCW), 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3274357>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 30. Keyes, Os. 2019. 'Discursive Harms'. *Real Life*, 19 December 2019. <https://reallifemag.com/discursive-harms/>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 31. ———. 2020. 'Automating Autism: Disability, Discourse, and Artificial Intelligence'. *The Journal of Sociotechnical Critique* 1 (1).
-

- <https://doi.org/10.25779/89bj-j396>, accessed 21.05.2024.
32. Martin Moruno, Dolores. 2016. 'Pain as Practice in Paolo Mantegazza's Science of Emotions'. *Osiris* 31: 137–62.
 33. McStay, Andrew. 2018. *Emotional AI: The Rise of Empathic Media*. SAGE.
 34. Miceli, Milagros, Tianling Yang, Laurens Naudts, Martin Schuessler, Diana Serbanescu, and Alex Hanna. 2021. 'Documenting Computer Vision Datasets: An Invitation to Reflexive Data Practices', In *Proceedings of the 2021 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency* (pp. 161-172).
 35. Mills, Mara, and Meredith Whittaker. 2019. 'Disability, Bias, and AI'. (AI Now Institute Report). <https://ainowinstitute.org/disabilitybiasai-2019.pdf>
 36. Mitchell, Margaret, Simone Wu, Andrew Zaldivar, Parker Barnes, Lucy Vasserman, Ben Hutchinson, Elena Spitzer, Inioluwa Deborah Raji, and Timnit Gebru. 2019. 'Model Cards for Model Reporting'. *Proceedings of the Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency, January*, 220–29. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3287560.3287596>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 37. Peña Gangadharan, Seeta, and Jędrzej Niklas. 2019. 'Decentering Technology in Discourse on Discrimination'. *Information, Communication & Society* 22 (7): 882–99. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2019.1593484>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 38. Picard, Rosalind W. 2000. *Affective Computing*. MIT Press.
 39. Raji, Inioluwa Deborah, and Genevieve Fried. 2021. 'About Face: A Survey of Facial Recognition Evaluation'. ArXiv:2102.00813 [Cs], February. <http://arxiv.org/abs/2102.00813>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 40. Rhue, Lauren. 2018. 'Racial Influence on Automated Perceptions of Emotions'. SSRN Scholarly Paper ID 3281765. Rochester, NY: Social Science Research Network. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3281765>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 41. Scheuerman, M., Kandrea Wade, Caitlin Lustig, and J. Brubaker. 2020. 'How We've Taught Algorithms to See Identity: Constructing Race and Gender in Image Databases for Facial Analysis'. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3392866>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 42. Sloane, Mona, E. Moss, O. Awomolo, and Laura Forlano. 2020. 'Participation Is Not a Design Fix for Machine Learning'. ArXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2007.02423>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 43. Sloane, Mona, Emanuel Moss, and Rumman Chowdhury. 2022. 'A Silicon Valley Love Triangle: Hiring Algorithms, Pseudo-Science, and the Quest for

- Auditability'. *Patterns* 3 (2): 100425. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2021.100425>, accessed 21.05.2024.
44. Spiel, Katta, Christopher Frauenberger, Os Keyes, and Geraldine Fitzpatrick. 2019. 'Agency of Autistic Children in Technology Research—A Critical Literature Review'. *ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction* 26 (November): 1–40. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3344919>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 45. Stark, Luke. 2020. 'The Emotive Politics of Digital Mood Tracking'. *New Media & Society* 22 (11): 2039–57. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444820924624>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 46. Stark, Luke, and Jevan Hutson. 2021. 'Physiognomic Artificial Intelligence'. *Fordham Intellectual Property, Media & Entertainment Law Journal*, Forthcoming, September. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3927300>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 47. Stilgoe, Jack, Richard Owen, and Phil Macnaghten. 2013. 'Developing a Framework for Responsible Innovation'. *Research Policy* 42 (9): 1568–80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2013.05.008>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 48. Tonekaboni, Sana, Shalmali Joshi, Melissa D. McCradden, and Anna Goldenberg. 2019. 'What Clinicians Want: Contextualizing Explainable Machine Learning for Clinical End Use'. *ArXiv:1905.05134 [Cs, Stat]*, August. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1905.05134>, accessed 21.05.2024.
 49. Zhang, Lanlan, Elizabeth A. Reynolds Losin, Yoni K. Ashar, Leonie Koban, and Tor D. Wager. 2021. 'Gender Biases in Estimation of Others' Pain'. *The Journal of Pain* 22 (9): 1048–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpain.2021.03.001>, accessed 21.05.2024.
-

This fellowship ran from January-May 2023 as part of BRAID.

BRAID is a UK-wide programme dedicated to integrating Arts and Humanities research more fully into the Responsible AI ecosystem, as well as bridging the divides between academic, industry, policy and regulatory work on responsible AI. Funded by the Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC), BRAID represents AHRC's major investment in enabling responsible AI in the UK. The Programme runs from 2022 to 2028. Working in partnership with the Ada Lovelace Institute and BBC, BRAID supports a network of interdisciplinary researchers and partnering organisations through the delivery of funding calls, community building events, and a series of programmed activities. Funding reference: Arts and Humanities Research Council grant number AH/X007146/1.

Learn more at www.braiduk.org

This research was supported via UK Research and Innovation by the R&D Science and Analysis Programme at the Department for Culture, Media & Sport. Any primary research, subsequent findings or recommendations do not represent Government views or policy and are produced according to research ethics, quality assurance, and academic independence.

To request an alternative format of this report please email braid@ed.ac.uk.

